

Therapeutic considerations in herpes-associated secondary glaucoma – clinical cases

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Abstract

Herpetic uveitis, most commonly caused by herpes simplex virus (HSV) and varicella-zoster virus (VZV), is a frequent cause of secondary glaucoma. Elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) in these patients is primarily due to inflammatory trabeculitis, trabecular meshwork obstruction, and steroid-induced mechanisms. IOP control is often challenging, and some cases require surgical intervention. Two patients without prior glaucoma developed refractory IOP elevation following herpetic uveitis. Clinical evaluation included tonometry, biomicroscopy, and monitoring of responses to medical and surgical therapy. Both patients received systemic antiviral therapy with valacyclovir. Medical antiglaucoma treatment alone failed to achieve adequate IOP control. In the first patient, glaucoma developed after active herpetic uveitis; in the second, after cataract surgery in an eye with a history of herpetic infection. Following preoperative antiviral preparation, trabeculectomy was performed, resulting in stable postoperative IOP. Herpetic secondary glaucoma can present with refractory IOP even in patients without prior glaucoma, and timely antiviral therapy and surgical management are essential for long-term control.

Keywords

Antiviral therapy, herpetic uveitis, trabeculectomy, uveitic glaucoma

Introduction

Herpes viruses are widespread pathogens that cause diseases with a diverse clinical presentation. Eight different herpes viruses have been identified, including six that cause ocular diseases: herpes simplex viruses 1 and 2 (HSV1, HSV2), varicella zoster virus (VZV), Epstein–Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, and human herpesvirus 8, which is involved in the pathogenesis of Kaposi's sarcoma. Of these, HSV and VZV are the most common ocular pathogens, each with an estimated incidence of 10 to 20 per 100,000 people per year (Liesegang et al. 1989). They are distinguished by their ability to adapt to a wide range of environmental conditions. A characteristic feature is their capacity to cause latent infections

in target organs, which carry a high risk of reactivation and the occurrence of recurrent disease. These infections can involve practically all structures of the eye and may lead to severe complications, including irreversible impairment of visual function. The clinical manifestations of ocular HSV and VZV infections vary widely but include blepharitis, conjunctivitis, scleritis, keratitis, anterior uveitis, necrotizing retinitis, choroiditis, and optic neuritis. They are the most common infectious causes of anterior uveitis (Jakob et al. 2009). Although the diagnosis of herpetic iridocyclitis is usually straightforward in the presence of skin lesions or dendritic keratitis, it can be challenging in their absence. Patients typically present with nonspecific complaints such as blurred vision, redness, pain, and photophobia. When

evaluating patients, both the possibility of a post-infectious condition, such as following a streptococcal infection (Markov et al. 2023a), and immune-mediated uveitis associated with systemic syndromes, such as Kawasaki disease (Bachmeyer et al. 2000) and Blau syndrome (Jindal et al. 2021), should be considered. Biomicroscopic features suggestive of a diagnosis of anterior herpetic uveitis include corneal edema, reduced corneal sensitivity, endothelial precipitates, markedly elevated intraocular pressure, and iris atrophy. In addition, anterior herpetic uveitis is almost always unilateral (Markov et al. 2022a).

The pathogenesis of secondary glaucoma caused by herpetic infection remains a subject of discussion. Trabeculitis, or inflammation of the trabecular meshwork, has been proposed as one of the main mechanisms leading to elevated intraocular pressure in herpetic uveitis (Sng et al. 2015). Infiltration of inflammatory immune cells, such as neutrophils, macrophages, and T cells, can obstruct the trabecular meshwork and Schlemm's canal either through direct cytotoxicity or via the release of proinflammatory cytokines and enzymes, resulting in glaucomatous changes (Sng et al. 2015; Pohlmann et al. 2020). Studies have also described the role of optineurin in ocular HSV-1 infection, indicating that it is essential for controlling HSV-1 infection, the associated inflammation, and subsequent neurodegenerative pathology. In experimental mouse models infected with HSV-1 and deficient in optineurin, severe consequences were observed both locally in the eye and within the central nervous system (Ames et al. 2021).

Other reported potential causes of secondary glaucoma following herpetic infection include the formation of posterior synechiae and pupillary block, leading to angle-closure glaucoma, as well as increased viscosity of the aqueous humor due to elevated levels of proteins, fibrin, and inflammatory cells (Epstein et al. 1978; Tiwari et al. 2005). Some authors have suggested that the elevated intraocular pressure is not secondary to inflammation but rather develops as a result of steroid therapy (Thygeson 1967). In contrast, another study reported that all patients had elevated intra-

ocular pressure prior to the initiation of steroid treatment (Pavan-Langston and Brockhurst 1969). The possibility of preexisting ocular hypertension or glaucoma should also not be excluded, highlighting the importance of recognizing the dual mechanisms underlying the disease.

Herpetic anterior uveitis can be misdiagnosed, as its manifestations may mimic the clinical features of Posner-Schlossman syndrome or Fuchs heterochromic iridocyclitis. Posner-Schlossman syndrome, also known as glaucomatocyclitic crisis, is characterized by acute, unilateral, recurrent episodes of elevated intraocular pressure accompanied by mild anterior chamber inflammation. The pathophysiology remains unclear, although several theories have been proposed, ranging from autoimmune to infectious mechanisms. While individual attacks typically resolve without sequelae, recurrent episodes over time can lead to long-term glaucomatous damage (secondary glaucoma). Associations have also been described between Posner-Schlossman syndrome and systemic infections, including *Helicobacter pylori*, suggesting a possible role for immunological mechanisms (Markov et al. 2023b). Treatment is focused on controlling intraocular pressure and reducing inflammation. However, in some cases, filtration surgery for glaucoma may be indicated to prevent spikes in intraocular pressure and to reduce the severity and frequency of attacks. Fuchs heterochromic iridocyclitis resembles herpetic uveitis due to the presence of iris atrophy, transillumination defects, and elevated intraocular pressure. In Fuchs syndrome, however, iris atrophy tends to be stromal and concentrated on the iris sphincter rather than full thickness; transillumination defects are typically radial rather than sectoral; and elevated intraocular pressure reflects cumulative trabecular meshwork damage rather than transient trabeculitis and therefore does not respond to topical corticosteroid or antiviral therapy. Additionally, patients with Fuchs uveitis syndrome are less likely to develop posterior synechiae, whereas posterior synechiae are frequently observed in patients with herpetic anterior uveitis (Velilla et al. 2021) (Table 1).

Table 1. Differential diagnosis between herpetic anterior uveitis, Posner-Schlossman syndrome, and Fuchs uveitis syndrome.

Feature	Herpetic anterior uveitis	Posner-Schlossman syndrome	Fuchs uveitis syndrome
Laterality	Usually unilateral	Usually unilateral	Usually unilateral
Onset	Acute or recurrent	Acute, episodic	Insidious, chronic
IOP	Elevated during active uveitis (may spike)	Markedly elevated during attacks, usually transient	Mild to moderate, gradually progressive
Anterior chamber inflammation	Moderate to severe; keratic precipitates (sectoral or central)	Mild; few keratic precipitates	Mild; diffuse fine keratic precipitates
Keratic precipitates	Large, granulomatous, or non-granulomatous; may be sectoral	Small, fine, few	Diffuse, fine, stellate
Iris changes	Sectoral atrophy common	Usually no atrophy	Diffuse stromal atrophy, heterochromia common
Corneal involvement	May have dendritic lesions or decreased sensitivity	Rare	Rare
Response to antivirals	Positive	No effect	No effect
Response to steroids	Rapid improvement if antiviral coverage established	May reduce inflammation, but IOP spikes recur	Mild improvement; IOP usually persists
Recurrence pattern	Recurrent, triggered by stress or immune changes	Episodic IOP spikes	Chronic, low-grade inflammation

Materials and methods

The first clinical case concerns a 64-year-old patient with no previous history of glaucoma. Several years prior to presentation, he had been diagnosed with herpetic uveitis, which was followed by a marked elevation in intraocular pressure. At that time, antiglaucoma therapy had been initiated, but the patient later discontinued the treatment. At presentation to the clinic, the patient reported decreased vision, ocular pain, photophobia, tearing, and redness in the right eye. Slit-lamp examination demonstrated signs of active iridocyclitis, including ciliary injection, keratic precipitates on the corneal endothelium, and inflammatory cells in the anterior chamber. Fundus examination revealed a pale optic disc with a cup-to-disc ratio of 0.9, suggestive of advanced glaucomatous damage (Fig. 1).

Best-corrected visual acuity was 0.5, and intraocular pressure measured 35 mmHg. Serological evaluation showed elevated IgG antibody levels against HSV and VZV, supporting a viral etiology. Treatment was initiated with systemic antiviral therapy using oral valacyclovir at a dose of 3 g/day, in combination with topical corticosteroids administered four times daily. Antiglaucoma therapy consisted of a fixed combination of dorzolamide/timolol twice daily, brimonidine tartrate twice daily, and oral acetazolamide 250 mg twice daily. Although the inflammatory signs gradually subsided with treatment, intraocular pressure remained inadequately controlled, fluctuating between 25 and 30 mmHg over the following month despite maximal tolerated medical therapy. In view of the persistent ocular hypertension and the risk of further optic nerve damage, surgical management was considered necessary, and trabeculectomy was performed to achieve better intraocular pressure control.

The second clinical case involves a 55-year-old patient with a history of iridocyclitis in the left eye due to varicella-zoster virus 3 years prior to presentation. Since then, she has maintained elevated intraocular pressure around 25 mmHg while on dorzolamide/timolol 2 times daily and brimonidine tartrate 2 times daily. On examination, visual acuity was 0.3, intraocular pressure was 27 mmHg, the anterior segment was quiet with fine old endothelial precipitates, the lens showed posterior subcapsular opacification, and the optic disc appeared pale with a cup-to-disc ratio of 0.5. The patient was offered phacoemulsification with intraocular lens implantation to improve vision. Preoperative preparation included oral valacyclovir 1.5 g/day for 2 weeks before surgery, as well as a single peribulbar injection of betamethasone. Postoperative management included levofloxacin/dexamethasone 6 times daily in a tapering regimen and continuation of antiviral therapy for 1 month. Two weeks after cessation of therapy, the patient presented again with complaints of ocular irritation, redness, and photophobia in the operated eye, raising suspicion for reactivation of intraocular inflammation. Slit-lamp examination revealed clinical findings consistent with recurrent iridocyclitis. The conjunctiva showed mild ciliary injection, and the anterior chamber demonstrated inflammatory activity with the presence of cells and a mild flare. Fine keratic precipitates were observed on the corneal endothelium, consistent with the patient's prior history of viral uveitis. The recurrence of iridocyclitis following cataract surgery suggested a possible reactivation of the underlying viral infection. Considering the patient's history and clinical findings, prompt treatment was initiated with systemic antiviral therapy consisting of oral valacyclovir at a dose of 3 g/day, combined with topical corticosteroid therapy administered four times daily to control the inflammatory response. Over the following period, the inflammatory signs gradually

Figure 1. Optical coherence tomography of the right optic nerve.

Table 2. Baseline characteristics of patients.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2
Viral etiology	HSV/VZV serology positive	Varicella-zoster virus (history)
History of glaucoma	None	None (chronically elevated IOP)
Trigger for IOP elevation	Active herpetic uveitis	After cataract surgery in the eye with prior viral uveitis
Symptoms at presentation	Decreased vision, pain, photophobia, tearing, redness	Decreased vision initially; later redness, irritation, photophobia
Visual acuity	0.5	0.3
Intraocular pressure	35 mmHg	27 mmHg
Anterior segment findings	Active iridocyclitis, keratic precipitates, AC cells	Initially quiet eye with old KPs; later recurrent iridocyclitis
Lens status	Clear/not significant	Posterior subcapsular cataract
Optic nerve	Pale disc, C/D 0.9	Pale disc, C/D 0.5
Antiglaucoma therapy	Dorzolamide/timolol, brimonidine, oral acetazolamide	Dorzolamide/timolol, brimonidine
Indication for surgery	Persistent elevated IOP	Persistent elevated IOP

subsided, and the anterior chamber reaction improved with treatment. However, despite adequate control of the inflammatory process, intraocular pressure remained persistently elevated at approximately 25 mmHg. Given the insufficient response to medical therapy and the risk of further glaucomatous damage, a decision was made to proceed with trabeculectomy to achieve more effective and long-term intraocular pressure control (Table 2).

Results

In both patients, trabeculectomy was performed with the primary aim of achieving sustained intraocular pressure control and preventing further glaucomatous optic nerve damage. Given the viral etiology of the uveitis and the known risk of postoperative reactivation, careful preoperative preparation was undertaken. This included systemic antiviral prophylaxis with oral valacyclovir at a dose of 3 g/day for 2 weeks prior to surgery to minimize the risk of viral reactivation and to ensure adequate control of subclinical inflammation. In addition, a single peribulbar injection of betamethasone was administered preoperatively to further suppress inflammatory activity and reduce the likelihood of postoperative inflammatory complications that could compromise surgical success. Following surgery, antiviral therapy with valacyclovir was continued using a gradual tapering regimen designed to maintain antiviral coverage during the postoperative phase. The regimen consisted of 3 g/day for 1 week, followed by 2 g/day for 1 week, 1.5 g/day for 1 week, and finally 1 g/day for 1 week. This stepwise reduction allowed

continued suppression of viral activity while minimizing the potential for adverse systemic effects associated with prolonged high-dose antiviral therapy. During the postoperative follow-up period, both patients were closely monitored through regular clinical examinations. Particular attention was paid to signs of recurrent intraocular inflammation, bleb function, and intraocular pressure levels. In addition, laboratory monitoring of liver and renal function was performed, given the prolonged systemic antiviral therapy. As a result of the combined surgical and medical management approach, a sustained reduction in intraocular pressure to ≤ 15 mmHg was achieved in both patients. Despite the successful pressure control following trabeculectomy, both patients continued their prescribed topical antiglaucoma therapy as an adjunctive measure to maintain long-term stability and reduce the risk of future IOP elevation (Table 3).

Discussion

The treatment of glaucoma in herpetic uveitis depends on several factors: management of the underlying disease, control of inflammation, and reduction of elevated intraocular pressure. The regimen includes both systemic and topical antiviral agents. Oral antivirals are used when the stroma or endothelium is involved or when there are concerns about surface toxicity from topical antivirals. Although the Herpetic Eye Disease Study did not demonstrate a statistically significant benefit of oral acyclovir in the treatment of HSV iridocyclitis (Herpetic Eye Disease Study Group 1996), most clinicians prescribe long-term

Table 3. Perioperative management and outcomes after trabeculectomy.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2
Surgical procedure	Trabeculectomy	Trabeculectomy
Preoperative antiviral prophylaxis	Valacyclovir 3 g/day for 2 weeks	Valacyclovir 3 g/day for 2 weeks
Preoperative steroid	Single peribulbar betamethasone injection	Single peribulbar betamethasone injection
Postoperative antiviral regimen	Valacyclovir taper (3 g 2 g 1.5 g 1 g weekly)	Valacyclovir taper (3 g 2 g 1.5 g 1 g weekly)
Postoperative monitoring	Inflammation, liver, and kidney function	Inflammation, liver, and kidney function
Postoperative intraocular pressure	14 mmHg	12 mmHg
Need for continued antiglaucoma therapy	Yes	Yes

systemic antiviral therapy in an attempt to reduce the risk of recurrence. Once antiviral coverage is ensured, corticosteroids exert a rapid effect on the inflammatory aspects of the disease, particularly intraocular inflammation, with a notable reduction in intraocular pressure within a few days. During prolonged steroid use, the possibility of steroid-induced ocular hypertension should be considered. However, a decrease in intraocular pressure due to steroid suppression of trabeculitis will precede any steroid-induced elevation of pressure (Thygeson 1967). A common mistake is underestimating inflammation out of concern for steroid-induced intraocular pressure elevation, but the dosage and frequency of steroids require careful monitoring. Laser trabeculoplasty may be considered for elevated intraocular pressure due to a steroid response, but the procedure is generally not recommended in patients with active uveitis due to the risk of exacerbating inflammation (Rubin et al. 2008). If intraocular pressure remains elevated despite control of intraocular inflammation, the use of topical and systemic pressure-lowering agents may be considered, including beta-blockers, oral and topical carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, and topical α 2-agonists. The use of prostaglandin analogs in patients with uveitis remains controversial. Some studies advise against their use due to an increased risk of disruption of the blood–aqueous barrier, anterior uveitis (1–6.4%), HSV keratitis reactivation, and cystoid macular edema (Warwar et al. 1998). Another study comparing latanoprost with a fixed combination of dorzolamide and timolol demonstrated similar efficacy

and no difference in the frequency of inflammatory recurrences (Markomichelakis et al. 2009). Current recommendations allow the use of prostaglandin analogs in uveitic glaucoma, but their application is primarily advised when other therapeutic options have failed and in the absence of active inflammation or cystoid macular edema (Fortuna et al. 2008). If a patient's intraocular pressure remains elevated despite maximally tolerated medical therapy, various surgical options may be considered, such as trabeculectomy or different drainage devices. Implantation of a drainage device is currently the preferred procedure, given its higher postoperative success rate in controlling intraocular pressure (Da Mata et al. 1999; Ceballos et al. 2002; Iverson et al. 2015). In uveitic glaucoma, trabeculectomy is more successful when combined with an antimetabolite (50%–67%) compared to without (30%). The use of mitomycin C has not shown a clear advantage over 5-fluorouracil (Ceballos et al. 2002). Preoperative topical and systemic corticosteroid therapy can help control ocular inflammation and minimize postoperative fibrosis. Cyclodestructive procedures have proven effective but carry a higher risk of hypotony compared to eyes with non-uveitic glaucoma, likely due to chronic reduction in aqueous humor production associated with uveitis (Murphy et al. 2003) (Fig. 2).

In patients with uveitis, it is critical to determine the exact etiology, as different causative agents require distinct therapeutic approaches. Special attention should be given to syphilis, which can present as anterior, posterior, or pan-uveitis and is often masked as other forms of

Figure 2. Treatment algorithm.

inflammation. Accurate diagnosis through patient history, clinical examination, and serological testing is essential, since antibiotic treatment for syphilis differs fundamentally from therapy for viral, immune-mediated, or traumatic uveitis, and is crucial for preventing complications such as secondary glaucoma, cataract, or permanent retinal damage (Zhang et al. 2017; Markov et al. 2022b).

The presented cases illustrate the typical diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in secondary glaucoma of herpetic etiology. Inflammatory trabeculitis is a key pathophysiological mechanism for elevated intraocular pressure in herpetic uveitis and often explains the limited response to standard antiglaucoma medications. Medical management in these patients is constrained both by the inflammatory process and by potential side effects. Antiviral therapy plays a central role not only in treating active uveitis but also in preventing recurrences, particularly in the context of surgical intervention. Surgical management of herpetic secondary glaucoma remains challenging due to an increased risk of inflammatory complications and filtration surgery failure. Nevertheless, trabeculectomy remains an effective option in refractory cases when performed with well-controlled inflammation. Cataract surgery, as observed in the second case, can act as a trigger for intraocular pressure elevation in patients with a history of herpetic uveitis, emphasizing the need for careful preoperative evaluation and antiviral prophylaxis.

Conclusion

Effective management of secondary glaucoma with herpetic etiology requires a multifaceted therapeutic approach. Antiviral therapy is essential to control viral replication, reduce intraocular inflammation, and prevent recurrences, forming the foundation for both medical and surgical interventions. Intraocular pressure should be carefully monitored and treated with appropriate topical and systemic agents, while recognizing the limitations imposed by inflammation and potential steroid responses. When medical therapy fails to achieve target pressure, timely surgical intervention—preferably trabeculectomy

or drainage devices performed under controlled inflammatory conditions—remains the most reliable option. Individualized treatment plans and vigilant monitoring are critical to optimize outcomes and minimize long-term complications such as optic nerve damage or vision loss.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Ames J, Yadavalli T, Suryawanshi R, Hopkins J, Agelidis A, Patil C, Fredericks B, Tseng H, Valyi-Nagy T, Shukla D (2021) OPTN is a host intrinsic restriction factor against neuroinvasive HSV-1 infection. *Nature Communications* 12(1): 5401. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25642-z>
- Bachmeyer C, Turc Y, Curan D, Duval-Arnould M (2000) Anterior uveitis as the initial sign of adult Kawasaki syndrome (mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome). *American Journal of Ophthalmology* 129(1): 101–2. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9394\(99\)00285-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9394(99)00285-8)
- Ceballos EM, Beck AD, Lynn MJ (2002) Trabeculectomy with antiproliferative agents in uveitic glaucoma. *Journal of Glaucoma* 11(3): 189–96. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00061198-200206000-00005>
- Ceballos EM, Parrish RK 2nd, Schiffman JC (2002) Outcome of Baerveldt glaucoma drainage implants for the treatment of uveitic glaucoma. *Ophthalmology* 109(12): 2256–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0161-6420\(02\)01294-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0161-6420(02)01294-0)
- Da Mata A, Burk SE, Netland PA, Baltatzis S, Christen W, Foster CS (1999) Management of uveitic glaucoma with Ahmed glaucoma valve implantation. *Ophthalmology* 106(11): 2168–72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-6420\(99\)90500-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-6420(99)90500-6)
- Epstein DL, Hashimoto JM, Grant WM (1978) Serum obstruction of aqueous outflow in enucleated eyes. *American Journal of Ophthalmology* 86(1): 101–5. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9394\(78\)90023-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9394(78)90023-5)

- Fortuna E, Cervantes-Castañeda RA, Bhat P, Doctor P, Foster CS (2008) Flare-up rates with bimatoprost therapy in uveitic glaucoma. *American Journal of Ophthalmology* 146(6): 876–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajo.2008.08.022>
- Herpetic Eye Disease Study Group (1996) A controlled trial of oral acyclovir for iridocyclitis caused by herpes simplex virus. *Archives of Ophthalmology* 114: 1065–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophth.1996.01100140267002>
- Iverson SM, Bhardwaj N, Shi W, Sehi M, Greenfield DS, Budenz DL, Kishor K (2015) Surgical outcomes of inflammatory glaucoma: a comparison of trabeculectomy and glaucoma-drainage-device implantation. *Japanese Journal of Ophthalmology* 59(3): 179–86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10384-015-0372-6>
- Jakob E, Reuland MS, Mackensen F, Harsch N, Fleckenstein M, Lorenz HM, Max R, Becker MD (2009) Uveitis subtypes in a German interdisciplinary uveitis center—analysis of 1916 patients. *J Rheumatol* 36(1): 127–36. <https://doi.org/10.3899/jrheum.080102>
- Jindal AK, Paliana RK, Suri D, Gupta A, Gattorno M, Ceccherini I, Kumar N, Bansal R, Nada R, Singh S (2021) A young female with early onset arthritis, uveitis, hepatic, and renal granulomas: a clinical tryst with Blau syndrome over 20 years and case-based review. *Rheumatology International* 41(1): 173–181. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-019-04316-6>
- Liesegang TJ, Melton LJ 3rd, Daly PJ, Ilstrup DM (1989) Epidemiology of ocular herpes simplex. Incidence in Rochester, Minn, 1950 through 1982. *Archives of Ophthalmology* 107(8): 1155–9. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophth.1989.01070020221029>
- Markomichelakis NN, Kostakou A, Halkiadakis I, Chalkidou S, Papa-konstantinou D, Georgopoulos G (2009) Efficacy and safety of latanoprost in eyes with uveitic glaucoma. *Graefes Archive for Clinical and Experimental Ophthalmology* 247(6): 775–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00417-009-1036-3>
- Markov G, Zdravkov Y, Oscar A (2023b) *Helicobacter pylori* and Uveitis: A Brief Narrative Literature Review. *Sriwijaya Journal of Ophthalmology* 6(2): 276–278. <https://doi.org/10.37275/sjo.v6i2.109>
- Markov G, Zdravkov Y, Oscar A (2023a) Post-Streptococcal Uveitis: A Narrative Literature Review. *Sriwijaya Journal of Ophthalmology* 6(1): 257–261. <https://doi.org/10.37275/sjo.v6i1.104>
- Markov G, Andonova N, Zdravkov Y, Petrova E, Oscar A (2022b) Ocular Syphilis: A Case Series. *Bulgarian Review of Ophthalmology* 66: 24–28. <https://doi.org/10.14748/bro.v66i1.8376>
- Markov G, Hristova R, Andonova N, Petkova I, Zdravkov Y, Oscar A (2022a) Herpetic Uveitis: An Experience from a Tertiary Referral Center in Bulgaria. *Sriwijaya Journal of Ophthalmology* 5(2): 193–197. <https://doi.org/10.37275/sjo.v6i1.82>
- Murphy CC, Burnett CA, Spry PG, Broadway DC, Diamond JP (2003) A two centre study of the dose-response relation for transscleral diode laser cyclophotocoagulation in refractory glaucoma. *British Journal of Ophthalmology* 87(10): 1252–7. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjo.87.10.1252>
- Pavan-Langston D, Brockhurst RJ (1969) Herpes simplex panuveitis. *Archives of Ophthalmology* 81: 783–787. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archophth.1969.00990010785005>
- Pohlmann D, Pahlitzsch M, Schlickeiser S, Metzner S, Lenglinger M, Bertelmann E, Maier AB, Winterhalter S, Pleyer U (2020) Virus-associated anterior uveitis and secondary glaucoma: Diagnostics, clinical characteristics, and surgical options. *PLoS One* 15(2): e0229260. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229260>
- Rubin B, Taglienti A, Rothman RE, Marcus CH, Serle JB (2008) The effect of selective laser trabeculoplasty on intraocular pressure in patients with intravitreal steroid-induced elevated intraocular pressure. *Journal of Glaucoma* 17(4): 287–92. <https://doi.org/10.1097/IJG.0b013e318031676c>
- Sng CC, Ang M, Barton K (2015) Uveitis and glaucoma: new insights in the pathogenesis and treatment. *Progress in Brain Research* 221: 243–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.pbr.2015.06.008>
- Thygeson P (1967) Chronic herpetic keratouveitis. *Transactions of the American Ophthalmological Society* 65: 211–26. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1310269/>
- Tiwari V, Clement C, Scanlan PM, Kowlessur D, Yue BY, Shukla D (2005) A role for herpesvirus entry mediator as the receptor for herpes simplex virus 1 entry into primary human trabecular meshwork cells. *Journal of Virology* 79(20): 13173–9. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.79.20.13173-13179.2005>
- Velilla S, Dios E, Herreras JM, Calonge M (2021) Fuchs' heterochromic iridocyclitis: a review of 26 cases. *Ocular Immunology and Inflammation* 9(3): 169–75. <https://doi.org/10.1076/ocii.9.3.169.3964>
- Warwar RE, Bullock JD, Ballal D (1998) Cystoid macular edema and anterior uveitis associated with latanoprost use. Experience and incidence in a retrospective review of 94 patients. *Ophthalmology* 105(2): 263–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0161-6420\(98\)92977-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0161-6420(98)92977-3)
- Zhang T, Zhu Y, Xu G (2017) Clinical Features and Treatments of Syphilitic Uveitis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Ophthalmology* 2017: 6594849. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/6594849>